

The Impact Of Distance Education On The Development Of E-Learning Skills Among Students Of Al-Huson University College, In Light Of Corona Pandemic

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 02 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Al-Huson University College Students, Corona Pandemic, Distance Education, E- Learning Skills</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5550435</p>	<p><i>This study aims to identify the level of development in e-learning skills among students of Al-Huson University College, in light of distance education, by implementing the study instrument related to the development of e-learning skills, which consists of (37) items spread on three areas (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs and software) on a random sample that consists of (381) male and female students. The study results showed that the level of development in e-learning skills as a whole among students of Al-Huson University College came to a medium degree, where the area (use of Moodle) came in first place at a high level, followed by the area (electronic technical skills) in second place at a medium level, and came in third and last place the area (use of educational programs and software) at a medium level. Results also showed nonexistence of statistically significant differences at the level $(0.05 = \alpha)$ between the arithmetic means of the study sample members' estimates represented in students on the study tool items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole and each area of it, attributed to the gender, education level, and specialization variables.</i></p>

Introduction

The world is currently experiencing a crisis that is perhaps the most dangerous in our modern time, represented in the Corona pandemic crisis that has had a negative impact on all life activities and sectors, most importantly, education. According to the UNESCO report that entitled "Education disruption due to the new Coronavirus and the responsiveness to it", there are more than (100) countries that have closed all schools, universities, and educational institutions throughout this pandemic, which affected more than half of the world's students, and led to select distance education to continue the educational process. In light of the invasion of Corona epidemic in the world today and the measures taken by various countries to protect its citizens, which include students in universities, schools, and other educational institutions and come on top of these measures the imposition of a full and partial ban, where the educational institutions must replace traditional education with the distance education. This rapid and sudden shift has placed responsibility on the burden of university teachers, in general and the university students in particular, and it became necessary for everyone to employ e-learning and the different software needed for the distance education of these courses, materials, and classes (Hassan, 2020).

The world today is experiencing scientific and technological revolutions, where the technological development has become a feature and a characteristic of contemporary societies and has resulted in an increase among the different countries in the use of technology and its applications in the educational field, where the e-education has emerged to play its main role in solving problems that face the traditional education, such as lack of educational staff, the invasion of time and space barriers, and the difficult epidemiological conditions that have cast its shadow on the entire world. Due to the continuous development of new era, e-learning has gone beyond the mere provision of courses through websites, to include all requirements of managing the process of teaching and learning. Most distance learning platforms consider one of the most important e-learning management systems used by most universities worldwide, because of the interaction between students and their teachers on the one hand, and between students themselves on the other hand, through the virtual classes and discussion sessions, and the possibility of sending and correcting duties and tests easily (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020).

Several studies have indicated an impact of Corona pandemic on the entire world, such as the descriptive study of (Yulia, 2020) which confirmed the impact methods of Corona pandemic on the reformation of education in Indonesia. The study showed types of online learning strategies used by instructors in the world, due to the closure of universities to reduce the spread of COVID-19. The results of this study showed the advantages and the effectiveness of using Internet-based learning, the high speed of Corona epidemic impact on the educational system, the decline of traditional education methods, and the spread of distance education because it supports home learning, therefore reduces individuals' mixing and reduces the spread of the virus.

(Basilaia&Kvavadze, 2020) referred in their study to the experience of moving from school education to distance education during the spread of Corona epidemic in Georgia, by relying on the first week statistics of teaching process at one of the private schools and its experience in moving from face-to-face education to the distance education during the Corona pandemic. The study also showed that the transition between the traditional education and online education was successful, and it's possible to benefit from the system and skills acquired by teachers, and students, and school management in the Corona epidemic at different and disruptive situations, such as helping people with special needs who require additional hours, increasing the effectiveness of group teaching, increasing students' independency, or obtaining new skills. (Draissi& Yong, 2020) added that what worries about the Corona pandemic is the difficulty of universities to continuously overcome the obstacles that face students and instructors, as well as the investment in scientific research. The new teaching methods led to an increase in students' independence, where the additional duties for students were one of the most important measures of instructors to maintain the momentum of students' home work, and universities have worked to provide free access to several platforms or databases for electronic learning.

The modern trends of education technology have contributed to the emergence of new and sophisticated teaching and learning systems that have had the greatest impact on making positive developments and changes to the way students learn and methods used to deliver the scientific information to them, as well as the changes on the content and form of scheduled curriculum in line with these trends and in accordance with the emerging educational conditions in the world. One of the systems produced by the modern trends in education technology is the so-called e-learning, which relies on the employment of computers, Internet, and all types of interactive multimedia in the teaching process (Khalifa, 2010). E-learning refers to the reliance on modern technologies to provide educational content to students in an effective and interactive way through its positive characteristics, such as the reduction of time, effort, and economic cost and its great potential in promoting students' learning and improving their educational level effectively, as well as providing an exciting, interactive, and interesting educational environment for both teachers and students, where it will eliminate the time and place determinants, as well as allowing students to learn in light of their abilities, scientific capabilities, and cognitive levels (Al-Mezhar, 2010).

The e-learning system consists of inputs, processes, outputs, and feedback, where the implementation of this system requires a set of basic requirements and components that must be integrated together for the purpose of making the system and its various components succeed. If changes measured in years, the past 10 years (2010-2020) could be equivalent to decades because e-learning is considered as one of the most important outcome of digital age and its modern technologies, and it is the key pillar of future education due to its reliance on ICT, which changes many of the ways that individuals use to communicate, learn, and work (Kinsarah& Attar, 2012). Education has invested in the tremendous technological advancement of this era by taking advantage of the technologies inside the classroom and laboratories, and between the corridors of schools and universities, but the most exciting thing is to exploit the latest computer technologies, software, and communications in establishing flexible and interactive electronic learning that enables learners to access the required information with minimal effort and within determined time and place. The consecutive developments in ICT have clearly affected the education system in schools, institutes, centers, and universities where universities and scientific research centers have taken it upon themselves to develop and employ this technology to serve education and training (Al-Keilani, 2014).

Learning management systems (LMS) are interactive educational applications that serve the faculty and students by providing many technical or administrative educational tools, and it became more popular among different educational institutions due to the diversity of used tools and the existence of factors that affect the effectiveness of LMS, such as the appropriateness and simplicity of screen design, the easiness of course design tools, compatibility level of system technical management with the academic management, the easiness of education management and the system acceptance level to download the various multimedia files, availability level of flexibility, interaction, and tests, and type of communication methods. (Bashir, 2019) referred in his study to the effectiveness of e-learning and high learner satisfaction, and also indicated that e-learning interaction consists of 3D structure: learner efforts, feedback, and learning content while (Osman, et al., 2019) stressed on the effectiveness of e-learning and self-learning in comparison with the normal methods, and study results indicated an impact of self-learning strategy based on e-learning.

(Al-Harbi, 2012) emphasized that LMS are divided into two parts: open source LMS that used free of charge and no one has the right to sell it, and it's also subject to the development and modification such as Atutor, Dokeos, and Moodle. The second part is closed-source or commercial LMS, which is owned and developed by a for-profit company, and it is not allowed to be used without a license such as Web CT, Blackboard, Tadaros, and Samaek. The LMS/ Moodle is an open-source curriculum management system distributed under the General Public License (GPL) and designed using the educational principles to help learners create their courses online. The Moodle System according to (Ashour, 2009) is characterized by the existence of a forum to discuss the topics related to educational process, delivery of duties to teachers instead of e-mail, the presence of live

chat rooms, and the search in content-related topics, as well as the existence of ten virtual templates to change the interface as desired and the possibility of allowing students to select the appropriate learning method.

(Al-Samraie, 2014) confirmed that LMS/ Moodle can provide the advantage of providing learner interaction tools, which learners use to interact during their studies and include the following tools:

Advertisements: this tool allows the faculty members to post news, alerts, or ads they want to send to learners or a group of them, and the learners click the mouse on the ad key and a board or a panel appears, where learners can list its content either alphabetically or historically.

Calendar: this tool is designed to tell the learners about the timing of events related to the learning topic and alerts them about its time, such as lectures, online meetings, university face-to-face meetings, etc., and learners can add to it whatever events they want.

Tasks: tells learners what task to perform and allows them to organize it according to the subject or according to their personal visions, and the teacher may send a particular task to a particular learner without sending it to another learner.

Estimates: this tool is specific for learners' estimates and grades, whether in the interim or final exams.

Users Guide: this tool works as a guide for students who participate in a course to get to know each other.

Therefore, the development and growth of education in general and university in particular has depended on the availability, sustainability, and integration of informatics knowledge, as well as the availability of skills to optimally use it and employ it. At a time when e-learning skills have become a realistic presence in the university education, it is expected that the overall reliance on information received by the student will be reduced at the typical methods in the classroom. University education is seeking to optimize the time, effort, and energy of students who search for information via the Internet, and any other LMS and its forms, as well as tools and techniques that contribute to the improvement of educational process. Distance education using e-learning techniques develop the self-learning skills, which has become a contemporary trend in education and has been the result of a growing demand for knowledge on the one hand, and the weak potentials of universities to handle it on the other hand due to the cognitive and technological revolution that led to the emergence of thinking about ways to contribute to the availability of learning opportunities for those wishing to learn.

A recent trend has emerged which helps learners to plan to acquire knowledge themselves, and define what they need from it, where with the existence of modern communication methods students have access to a large number of libraries at the local and foreign universities, and became able to identify the topics they need. In addition, the number of search engines that can make them reach the heart of books and sources has increased (Bashir, Osman, Zakaria, Mohammed & Al-Jalabi, 2019). Self-learning has also become an educational requirement in this decade to cope with the rapid changes and give students the basic continuous cognitive and technical skills of learning. The psychological studies emphasize the importance of learners to educate themselves, where self-learning takes into account the individual differences between learners and develop the personality of learners in all aspects to be able to act independently, develop their personal responsibilities, and allow them to discover their own abilities. (Al-Rababah, 2020) emphasized the significant role that distance education plays in the development of self-learning among university students and their acquisition of many skills to handle the electronics and programs and obtain the desired knowledge and experience. Jaber (2020) also refers to the importance of computers, Internet, and computer skills availability on students' achievement in the different subjects and their acquisition of targeted knowledge and experience.

1. STUDY PROBLEMS

In light of the Corona pandemic, distance education has become the only option for educational institutions to complete the educational process, and its success in general and in front of Balqa Applied University and its counterparts from the Jordanian universities in particular, in light of the great technological development and the spread of modern methods, such as computers, Internet, and multimedia that offer audio, vocal, and interactive effects. Balqa Applied University has found itself forced to shift from the traditional face-to-face education on campus to the distance education style, by relying on the techniques provided by the university for the success of this type of education and to help its students to continue their learning. The University is keen on serving the interest of its students on the one hand and the national interest on the other hand to complete the process of giving, achieving, and succeeding in this homeland, in alignment with the national policy of our beloved country. This study came to reveal the role that distance education plays in developing students' skills related to the use and development of e-learning skills among students of Al-Huson University College, as one of Al-Balqa Applied University colleges.

Study Questions

The current study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the impact of distance education on the development of e-learning skills among students of Al-Huson University College?

2. Are there any statistically significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) between the arithmetic means of study sample members' (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills, as a whole and each of its areas attributed to gender, academic level, and specialization variables?

2. STUDY OBJECTIVES & IMPORTANCE

3.1 Objectives:

The objectives of the present study are:

- Determine the distance education level at Al-Balqa Applied University.
- Identify the e-learning level at Al-Balqa Applied University.
- Detect the relationship between distance education and the development of e-learning skills among students of Al-Huson University College/ Al-Balqa Applied University.

3.3 Importance:

The importance of this study stems from the fact that it is useful for the improvement of education outputs by promoting and developing e-learning among students and improving the level of distance education to ensure the continuation of distance education, in light of crises that stand in the way of educational process, and can benefit from the study instruments to measure the distance education and e-learning levels at the Jordanian universities, and also this study is considered as one of the educational historical records of Corona pandemic crisis.

3. STUDY METHODS & PROCEDURES

4.1 Study Limitations:

The present study suffers from the following limitations:

- Human Boundaries: this study is implemented on (381) male and female students from Al-Huson University College/ Al-Balqa Applied University.
- Temporal Boundaries: this study was implemented during the first semester of academic year (2020/2021).
- Objective Boundaries: this study addressed the impact of distance education on the development of e-learning skills, in light of Corona pandemic, and implemented the study tool which is related to development of e-learning skills and consists of (37) items distributed on three areas (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, and use of educational programs and software) through an electronic questionnaire distributed on students using the electronic learning techniques and social media. Therefore, the generalizations of the study results depend on the validity and reliability of study tools, and on the seriousness of the study sample responses on the items of study scale.

4.2 Study Population & Sample:

The study population consists of all the bachelor students at Al-Huson University College/ Al-Balqa Applied University in the first semester of the (2020/2021) academic year, and selected a random sample of the study population through the random categorical sample method, which contains (381) members distributed according to the study variables, as shown in table (1)

Table (1) Distribution of study sample members (students) according to their variables

Variable	Level/Category	Number	%
Gender	Male	182	47.8
	Female	199	52.2
	Total	381	100.0
Academic Level	First	38	10.0
	Second	99	26.0
	Third	89	23.4
	Fourth	155	40.7
	Total	381	100.0
Specialization	Humanity	180	47.2
	Sciences	201	52.8
	Total	381	100

4.3 Study Instruments:

The main instrument used in this study was a questionnaire that was developed electronically through returning to the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the study topic, and the questionnaire consisted of (37) items distributed on three areas:

- Electronic technical skills.

- Use of Moodle.
- Use of educational programs and software.

Researchers extracted the validity and reliability coefficient for the study tool, as follows:

First: Construct Validity for study instrument (development of e-learning skills)

Researchers verified the Construct Validity of study instrument related to the development of e-learning skills on a survey sample of (67) male and female students by calculating Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient for its items, as shown in table (2) below:

Table (2) Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient for study tool items related to the development of e-learning skills

Item Number	Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient		Item Number	Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient	
	Field it belong to	Study tool as a whole		Field it belong to	Study tool as a whole
1	0.58	0.55	20	0.57	0.56
2	0.66	0.62	21	0.73	0.58
3	0.72	0.64	22	0.78	0.71
4	0.70	0.62	23	0.80	0.63
5	0.76	0.70	24	0.75	0.60
6	0.68	0.64	25	0.59	0.60
7	0.68	0.66	26	0.54	0.63
8	0.72	0.73	27	0.22	0.47
9	0.63	0.62	28	0.53	0.43
10	0.78	0.74	29	0.61	0.43
11	0.66	0.59	30	0.78	0.69
12	0.61	0.55	31	0.78	0.66
13	0.66	0.64	32	0.68	0.66
14	0.73	0.50	33	0.74	0.61
15	0.50	0.49	34	0.78	0.59
16	0.74	0.58	35	0.77	0.70
17	0.80	0.64	36	0.70	0.56
18	0.78	0.66	37	0.57	0.57
19	0.83	0.66			

It is noticed from table (2) that all Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient values are greater than (0.20), which is acceptable for the purposes of current study.

Second: Study Instrument Reliability (development of e-learning skills)

To verify the reliability of study tool related to the development of e-learning skills, researchers estimated the internal consistency coefficients for the study tool as a whole and for each area of it using the Cornbach Alpha equation and the Pearson test- retest reliability coefficients equation, as shown in table (3) below:

Table (3): Internal consistency Cornbach Alpha coefficients & Pearson Test-Retest reliability coefficients for study tool as a whole and for each area of it

Area	Internal Consistency	Pearson Test-Retest
Electronic Technical Skills	0.93	0.84
Use of Moodle	0.94	0.89
Use of Educational Programs & Software	0.91	0.81
Study Instrument as a Whole	0.96	0.90

It is noticed from table (3) that the coefficient values of internal consistency were between (0.91-0.94) and for the instrument as a whole (0.96), while the coefficient values of Pearson Test-Retest were between (0.81-0.89) and for the instrument as a whole (0.90), and all of it is acceptable for current study purposes.

Third: statistical standard of study instrument (development of e-learning skills)

To determine the level of development in e-learning skills among students of Al-Huson Community College and for each field of it, the researchers used the statistical standard based on the arithmetic means, as shown in table (4)

Table (4) Statistical standard for determining the development level of e-learning skills among students of Al-Huson College and for each areas of it, based on arithmetic means

Arithmetic Means for each area	Level
1.00-less than 1.80	Very low
1.80-less than 2.60	Low
2.60-less than 3.40	Medium
3.40-less than 4.20	High
4.20-5.00	Very High

4.4 Study Variables: The study included the following variables:

First: Independent Variables

Gender: it has two categories (male, female)

Academic level: it has four levels (first year, second year, third year & fourth year)

Specialization: it has two categories (Humanity, Sciences)

Second: Dependent Variables

– Level of development in e-learning skills as a whole among Al-Huson College students represented by the arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to development of e-learning skills.

– Development areas in students' e-learning skills represented by the arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on each area of instrument (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs and software).

4.5 Statistical Analysis:

– To answer the first question, the researchers used the arithmetic means and standard deviations to calculate the development level of e-learning skills among Al-Huson College students.

– To answer the second question, the researchers used the arithmetic means and standard deviations according to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables, and also implemented Three Way ANOVA analysis to determine the statistical significance of apparent differences between the arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole. The arithmetic means and standard deviations were used according to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables, and used the Three Way MANOVA analysis to determine the statistical significance of apparent differences between the arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on each area of e-learning skills development items.

4. STUDY RESULTS, DISCUSSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Study Results & Discussions:

Results related to the first question. To answer the first question of this study “What is the impact of distance education on the development of e-learning skills among students of Al-Huson University College?” the researchers computed the arithmetic means and standard deviations of study sample members' estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole, and each area of it (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs & software), as shown in table (5) below:

Table (5) arithmetic means and standard deviations of study sample members' estimates on the study instrument items of e-learning skills' development as a whole, and each area of it in a descending order according to means

Number	Area	Mean*	STDEV	Rank	Level
2	Use of Moodle	3.46	0.80	1	High
1	Electronic Technical Skills	3.23	0.91	2	Medium
3	Use of educational programs & software	2.98	0.83	3	Medium
	Development of e-learning skills as a whole	3.24	0.73		Medium

* Lower degree (1) & higher degree (5) for each area

Table (5) showed that the development level of e-learning skills as a whole among students is medium with an arithmetic mean of (3.24) and a standard deviation of (0.73), where the second area (use of Moodle) came at first rank with a mean of (3.46) at high level, followed by the second place by the first area (electronic technical skills) with a mean of (3.23) at medium level, and the third area (use of educational programs and software) came third and in the last place with a mean of (2.98) at medium level.

The researchers also calculated the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample members' (students) estimates on each item of each study instrument area related to the development of e-learning skills (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs & software), as shown in table (6) below:

Table (6) Arithmetic means and standard deviations of study sample members' (students) estimates on each item of each study instrument area related to the development of e-learning skills, in a descending order according to means

Number	Item	Mean*	STDEV	Rank	Level
8	Send and receive messages with teacher through available e-methods	3.72	1.10	1	High
2	Use Internet to search for required educational materials	3.54	1.10	2	High
7	Design & produce proper courses & duties & send it to teachers or panel discussion	3.51	1.19	3	High
5	Store photos in a file and send it to teachers	3.43	1.26	4	High
9	Develop proper communication skills with teachers	3.41	1.20	5	High
1	Create a private E-mail	3.31	1.20	6	Medium
3	Convert a file from WORD to PDF format	3.28	1.31	7	Medium
6	Develop educational materials using PPTs	3.19	1.25	8	Medium
10	Create electronic groups between colleagues to interact and review the educational materials	3.09	1.23	9	Medium
13	Communicate with colleagues from other universities and share useful knowledge & experience with them	3.04	1.19	10	Medium
4	Convert a file from PDF to WORD format	3.03	1.35	11	Medium
11	Deal with images and convert it from one form to another	2.78	1.32	12	Medium
12	Deal with supported educational software, such as CAMERA SCAN	2.70	1.34	13	Medium
First Area: Electronic Technical Skills		3.23	0.91		Medium
14	Get in and out of the site properly	3.80	1.04	1	High
21	Followed life lectures through BBB Moodle	3.68	1.08	2	High
17	Download and send duties/ homework	3.66	1.02	3	High
23	Review everything downloaded by teachers	3.66	1.03	4	High
19	Deal with all forms and types of tests	3.62	1.01	5	High
16	Use the university's e-mail	3.59	1.04	6	High
24	See marks given on duties and exams and its total	3.51	1.08	7	High
18	Follow-up on educational materials ASAP	3.50	1.06	8	High
22	Communicate with teachers using e-messages	3.36	1.07	9	Medium
20	Delete or modify submitted duties	3.26	1.16	10	Medium
15	Change passwords	3.13	1.14	11	Medium
25	Communicate with colleagues through chat rooms	3.13	1.05	12	Medium
26	Download educational materials on site to help colleagues	3.06	1.15	13	Medium
Second Area: Use of Moodle		3.46	0.80		High
27	Use Microsoft team to attend lectures and perform the required activities	3.93	1.04	1	High
32	Train and give advice and guidance to colleagues about ways to deal with required educational software	3.17	1.07	2	Medium
37	Download the educational software from Internet on the device and delete it	3.12	1.18	3	Medium
35	Employ some software to produce duties and teaching materials appropriately	3.11	1.05	4	Medium
30	Use proper interactive software for course topic	2.98	1.14	5	Medium
31	Search for educational software that serve the course and provide it to teachers and colleagues	2.92	1.15	6	Medium
33	Entrance to electronic libraries and using it	2.85	1.12	7	Medium
34	Register and participate in scientific forums that serve the course topic	2.79	1.15	8	Medium
36	Create a private electronic library and put	2.69	1.16	9	Medium

	allrequired educational materials in it				
28	Use Zoom Software to attend lectures and perform required activities.	2.63	1.32	10	Medium
29	Use Google Class Room to attend lectures and perform required activities.	2.54	1.27	11	Low
Third Area: Use of educational programs & software		2.98	0.83		Medium
Instrument items as a whole (development of e-learning skills)		3.24	0.73		Medium

* Lower degree (1) & higher degree (5)

Table (6) shows that the arithmetic means for the first area items (electronic technical skills) were between (2.70-3.72) at levels between (medium) and (high) while the arithmetic means for second area items (use of Moodle) were between (3.06-3.80) at a level between (medium) and (high), and also the arithmetic means for third area items (use of educational programs & software) were between (2.54-3.72) at a level between (medium) and (high), which indicates a clear development in students' acquisition of e-learning skills that results from students' use of special educational techniques and distance education programs at the university. The majority of students displayed a high to medium level of improvement on all items of questionnaire, which indicated that students felt they had acquired many new skills while using the distance education system. These results agree with many previous studies that have indicated similar results, such as the study of (Osman, et al., 2019) which revealed a medium interaction of students with the new learning resources, their access to libraries, their dealings with computers, and their practices of self-learning processes, the study of (Draissi & Yong, 2020) which indicated an increase in students' education independent as a result of their use of new strategies related to distance education, in light of the Corona epidemic, and indicates their possession of new learning skills and their very large dependence on self-learning processes, while the study of (Yulia, 2020) tackled the effectiveness of distance education in the current circumstances and its impact on acquiring new skills among students.

(Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020) study found that transition between traditional and online education was successful, and it's possible to benefit from systems and skills acquired by teachers, students, and school management during the Corona epidemic, while (Al-Rababah, 2020 & Jaber, 2020) stressed in their studies on the importance of providing distance education infrastructure and its relationship with the degree of interaction, trends, and acquirement of new skills to deal with the distance education systems. In regard to the acquisition of second area which related to the use of Moodle on the first rank, it is normal because Balqa Applied University considers it the main platform for interacting with students, presenting duties, and attending lectures, therefore students interacted with it significantly and led them to acquire many skills and develop their old skills and knowledge in dealing with the Moodle system. All that was related to the achievement of course requirements, presentation of exams, and the course success or failure and here where students develop their skills individually, which led to the development of a responsibility and independence spirit in the processes of learning and gaining experience.

Results of second question, which stated: Are there any statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the arithmetic means of study sample members' (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills, as a whole and each of its areas attributed to gender, academic level, and specialization variables?

To answer this question, the researchers computed the arithmetic means and standard deviations of study sample members' (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole, due to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables, as shown in table (7) below:

Table (7) means and standard deviations of study sample members' estimates on study instrument items as a whole related to development of e-learning skills due to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables

Variable	Level/ Category	Mean	STDEV
Gender	Male	3.28	0.81
	Female	3.20	0.64
	Overall	3.24	0.73
Academic Level	First	3.19	0.67
	Second	3.30	0.71
	Third	3.21	0.72
	Fourth	3.22	0.77
	Overall	3.24	0.73
Specialization	Humanity	3.24	0.64
	Sciences	3.23	0.80
	Overall	3.24	0.73

It could be noticed from table (7) that there are apparent and clear differences between the arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole, due to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables, and to determine the statistical significance of these apparent differences, the researchers used the Three Way ANOVA analysis, as shown in table (8) below:

Table (8) results of Three Way ANOVA analysis for means of study sample members estimates on study instrument items related to development of e-learning skills as a whole, due to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables

Variable	SS	DF	MS	F-value	Sig.
Gender	0.724	1	0.724	1.351	0.246
Academic Level	0.683	3	0.228	0.425	0.735
Specialization	0.030	1	0.030	0.056	0.814
Error	201.073	375	0.536		
Adjusted Total	202.403	380			

Table (8) shows the following:

– The statistical significance value of gender variable amounted to (0.246), which is higher than the level ($\alpha=0.05$) and indicate nonexistence of statistically significant difference at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the two arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole, due to gender variable.

– The statistical significance value of academic level variable amounted to (0.735), which is higher than the level ($\alpha=0.05$) and indicate nonexistence of statistically significant difference at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the two arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole, due to academic level variable.

– The statistical significance value of specialization variable amounted to (0.814), which is higher than the level ($\alpha=0.05$) and indicate nonexistence of statistically significant difference at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the two arithmetic means of study sample members (students) estimates on the study instrument items related to the development of e-learning skills as a whole, due to specialization variable.

The researchers also calculated the arithmetic means and standard deviations of study sample members' estimates on each area of the study instrument related to the development of e-learning skills (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs and software) due to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables, as shown in table (9) below:

Table (9) means and standard deviations of study sample members' estimates on each area of study instrument related to development of e-learning skills due to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables

Variable	Level/Category	Electronic Technical Skills		Use of Moodle		Use of Educational Programs & Software	
		Mean	STDEV	Mean	STDEV	Mean	STDEV
Gender	Male	3.32	1.02	3.47	0.88	3.00	0.90
	Female	3.16	0.79	3.45	0.73	2.96	0.76
	Overall	3.23	0.91	3.46	0.80	2.98	0.83
Academic Level	First	3.18	0.95	3.32	0.69	3.06	0.69
	Second	3.27	0.92	3.56	0.82	3.03	0.77
	Third	3.16	0.86	3.44	0.79	3.00	0.84
	Fourth	3.26	0.92	3.44	0.82	2.91	0.89
	Overall	3.23	0.91	3.46	0.80	2.98	0.83
Specialization	Humanity	3.23	0.85	3.44	0.71	3.02	0.78
	Sciences	3.23	0.95	3.48	0.88	2.94	0.87
	Overall	3.23	0.91	3.46	0.80	2.98	0.83

It is noticed from table (9) that there are apparent and clear differences between the arithmetic means of study sample members' estimates on each area of study instrument related to the development of e-learning skills (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs & software) due to (gender, academic level & specialization) variables, and to determine the statistical significance of these apparent differences, researchers implemented the Three Way MANOVA analysis as shown in table (10) below:

Table (10) Results of Three Way MANOVA analysis for the arithmetic means of study sample members' estimates on each area of study instrument related to the development of e-learning skills, due to (gender, academic level, specialization) variables

Source of Variance	Area	SS	DF	MS	F-value	Sig.
Gender	Electronic Technical Skills	2.411	1	2.411	2.934	0.088

Hotelling's Trace=0.010 Sig.=0.275	Use of Moodle	0.061	1	0.061	0.095	0.758
	Use of Educational Programs & Software	0.540	1	0.540	0.785	0.376
Academic Level Wilks' Lambda=0.977 Sig.=0.471	Electronic Technical Skills	0.670	3	0.223	0.272	0.846
	Use of Moodle	1.979	3	0.660	1.019	0.384
	Use of Educational Programs & Software	1.175	3	0.392	0.570	0.635
Specialization Hotelling's Trace=0.005 Sig.=0.586	Electronic Technical Skills	0.081	1	0.081	0.098	0.754
	Use of Moodle	0.149	1	0.149	0.230	0.632
	Use of Educational Programs & Software	0.492	1	0.492	0.715	0.398
Error	Electronic Technical Skills	308.220	375	0.822		
	Use of Moodle	242.855	375	0.648		
	Use of Educational Programs & Software	257.936	375	0.688		
Adjusted Total	Electronic Technical Skills	311.441	380			
	Use of Moodle	244.991	380			
	Use of Educational Programs & Software	260.151	380			

Table (10) shows the following:

- The statistical significance value of Hotelling's Trace test due to the gender variable amounted to (0.275), which is higher than the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) and indicate the nonexistence of statistical significant difference at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the two arithmetic means of study sample members' estimates on areas of study instrument (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs & software), due to the gender variable.
- The statistical significance value of Wilks' Lambda test due to the academic level variable amounted to (0.471), which is higher than the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) and indicate the nonexistence of statistical significant difference at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the two arithmetic means of study sample members' estimates on areas of study instrument (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs & software), due to the academic level variable.
- The statistical significance value of Hotelling's Trace test due to the specialization variable amounted to (0.586), which is higher than the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) and indicate the nonexistence of statistical significant difference at the level ($\alpha=0.05$) between the two arithmetic means of study sample members' estimates on areas of study instrument (electronic technical skills, use of Moodle, use of educational programs & software), due to the specialization variable.

This result is attributed to the fact that distance education requirements and dealing with electronic systems in education are new experiences imposed by the circumstances of current epidemiological situation, which led to make multiple decisions to achieve the social divergence or spacing and create a safe health environment, therefore its new experiences for all groups, specialization, and academic level and indicate no difference between males and females because both are going through the same circumstances and exposed to the same experiences, as well as for specialization, whether it's humanity or sciences, the period requires the acquisition of new experiences that not owned by all specialization, nor does the academic level of student, whether it was in the fourth year or first one, they have equal level of previous experiences in this area, knowing that Moodle and e-learning systems exists on the university education system before this pandemic but was not properly activated and the majority of students were unaware of the way to deal with it. For these reasons, there were no statistically significant differences between these variables, and to know that results of this study contradict with some of the previous studies results, such as (Osman, et al., 2019) study and (Jaber, 2020) study.

5.2 Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the present study, it is recommended to:

- Hold training programs for students that guide them to deal with the electronic systems and distance education systems until it become certain that all students are acquiring the distance education skills.
- Include in the study plans for all specializations a compulsory course that contains distance education skills and ways to deal with educational software.
- Hold training courses for instructors to obtain high efficiency distance education skills.

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